

Supplemental materials

Figure S1: Chemical synthesis of CK arabinosides and their fluorinated counterparts

The starting compound with non-fluorinated or fluorinated arabinose was added into the flask followed by BOP, DIPEA and appropriate benzylamine in dry DMF. The reaction mixture was stirred 24 hrs at 55 - 60°C, evaporated and purified by column chromatography as previously published (Bryksova 2020a, Bryksova 2020b). The final product was obtained at a purity of >98%.

References

Bryksova, M., Dabravolski, S., Kučerova, Z., Zavadil Kokas, F., Špundova, M., Plihalova, L., Takac, T., Gruz, J., Hudeček, M., Hlouškova, V., Koprna, R., Novak, O., Strnad, M., Plihal, O., Doležal, K.: Aromatic cytokinin arabinosides promote PAMP-like responses and positively regulate leaf longevity. *ACS Chem Biol*, 2020a, 15(7), 1949-1963.

Bryksova, M., Hybenova, A., Esteban Hernandez, A., Novak, O., Pěņčık, A., Spıchal, L., De Diego, N., Doležal, K.: Hormoprimering for mitigating abiotic stress affects: A case study of N9-substituted cytokinin derivatives with fluorinated carbohydrate moiety. *Front Plant Sci*. 2020b, 11, 599228

Figure S2: CK arabinosides inhibit tomato disease more effectively than 6-BAP- soil drench experiments.

5-week-old "M82" tomato plants were treated with the indicated CK arabinosides (10 μ M), or the CK 6-BAP (100 μ M) by soil drench, and infected with *B. cinerea* mycelia from a 3-day culture (**A**) or *X. euvesicatoria* from overnight cultures ($OD_{600}=0.0002$), (**B**), 24 h after treatment. Lesion areas were measured using ImageJ, 72 hours after infection (**A**), or, bacterial colony forming units (CFU) were quantified by plating serial dilutions of macerated leaf tissue, 5 days after inoculation (**B**).

Boxplots represent inner quartile ranges (box), outer quartile ranges (whiskers), and median (line in box), all points shown. Experiment was repeated 3 independent times. Different letters indicate statistically significant differences among samples in Welch's ANOVA with Games-Howell's post-hoc test. A: $N>16$, $p<0.0061$; B: $N>21$, $p<0.03$.

Figure S3: Dose response of CK-arabinoside mediated gray mold disease inhibition.

5-week-old "M82" tomato plants were treated with ARA1 (A), F-ARA2 (B), or the control CK 6-BAP (C), at indicated concentrations, by foliar spray, and infected with *B. cinerea* mycelia from a 3-day culture, 24 h after treatment. Lesion areas were measured using ImageJ, 72 hours after infection. Bars indicate mean \pm SE, all points shown. Different letters indicate statistically significant differences among samples in one-way ANOVA with Tukey's post-hoc test. A: N>16, p<0.03; B: N>15, p<0.04; C: N>10, p<0.003. Disease reduction % indicated in green above bars.

Figure S4: CK arabinosides promote immune responses more effectively than 6-BAP-ethylene production.

5-week-old "M82" tomato plants were treated with the indicated CK arabinosides (10 μM), or the CK 6-BAP (100 or 10 μM) by foliar spray. 24h after treatment, ethylene production was quantified using a gas chromatograph in response to wounding or EIX. Bars indicate mean ±SE, all points shown. Experiment was repeated 2 independent times. Different letters indicate statistically significant differences among samples in Welch's ANOVA with Dunnett's post-hoc test. N>4, p<0.04.

Figure S5: Comparison of defense gene activation with CK treatment between 10 and 100 μM . 5-week-old "M82" tomato plants were treated with CK 6-BAP, at 10 or 100 μM . After 24h, leaf tissue was harvested, RNA and cDNA were prepared, and expression of the indicated defense genes was assayed using qRT-PCR. Bars indicate mean \pm SE, all points shown. Points represent independent biological repeats conducted on different plants, N>4. Asterisks mark significant increase in comparison with mock treatment, in Welch's ANOVA with Dunnett's post-hoc test, * p <0.05, ** p <0.01, *** p <0.001, **** p <0.0001, ns- non-significant.

A1

A2

B1

B2

Figure S6: pH stability assay

The chemical stability of two selected cytokinin arabinosides, ARA-1 (**A**) and F-ARA-3 (**B**), was assessed across a range of pH conditions. Stock solutions (10^{-2} M) were prepared in DMSO and diluted to 10^{-4} M using McIlvaine buffer (pH 3, 4, 5, 6, or 7) (McIlvaine, 1921). Samples were incubated at room temperature for either 1 hour or 24 hours and subsequently analyzed using an Acquity UPLC H-Class System (Waters, USA) coupled with a single quadrupole mass spectrometer (QDa) equipped with electrospray ionization. Mass spectra were acquired in the range of 45–1000 m/z, and UV absorbance was recorded from 190–500 nm.

Panels **A1** and **B1** display UV chromatograms of compounds **A** and **B**, respectively, after 24 hours of incubation at pH 3. In both cases, a single major UV peak corresponding to the intact compound was detected, indicating no detectable hydrolysis of the glycosidic bond. Panels **A2** and **B2** show mass spectra confirming the molecular mass of the intact arabinoside conjugates.

Chromatographic separation was achieved by injecting 5 μ L of each sample onto a reversed-phase Symmetry C18 column (5 μ m, 150 \times 2.1 mm; Waters, Milford, USA) at a flow rate of 0.4 mL/min. The mobile phase consisted of a binary gradient: starting with 5% solvent A, increasing linearly to 99% A over 25 minutes, followed by 5 minutes of isocratic elution at 90% A. Solvent A was 100% methanol; solvent B was 15 mM formic acid adjusted to pH 4 with ammonium hydroxide.

Reference

McIlvaine, T. C.: J. Biol. Chem. 1921, 183

Figure S7: CK arabinosides inhibit tomato disease through SA and ET pathways- leaf images.

5-week-old tomato plants of the SA deficient transgenic line *NahG* (background MoneyMaker –MM); The ET insensitive mutant *neveripe* (*nr*, background line Pearson-Pn); and the JA insensitive mutant *jai-1* (background M82) were treated with the indicated CK arabinosides, or the CK 6-BAP, at 10 μ M, by foliar spray, and infected with *B. cinerea* mycelia from a 3-day culture, 24 h after treatment. Representative leaves are depicted 72 hours after infection. Lesions marked with dotted ellipses.

Supplemental Figure S8- GO pathways upregulated with 6-BAP and CK arabinoside treatment.

Analysis was conducted on DEGs identified using the DESeq2 package ($\text{padj} < 0.05$, $\log_2\text{FC} > 1$), using Gene Ontology (GO).

Analysis and figures were generated using ShinyGo 0.82 at <https://bioinformatics.sdstate.edu/go/>.

Supplemental Figure S9- GO pathways downregulated with 6-BAP and CK arabinoside treatment.

Analysis was conducted on DEGs identified using the DESeq2 package ($\text{padj} < 0.05$, $\log_2\text{FC} > 1$), using Gene Ontology (GO). Analysis and figures were generated using ShinyGo 0.82 at <https://bioinformatics.sdstate.edu/go/>.

Downregulated KEGG pathways

Pathways downregulated by all 3 compounds:

Galactose metabolism
Beta-alanine metabolism
Metabolic pathways
Fructose and Mannose metabolism
Starch and sucrose metabolism
Propanoate metabolism
Carbon metabolism
Inositol phosphate metabolism
Amino sugar and nucleotide sugar metabolism
Nicotinate and nicotinamide metabolism
Valine, leucine and isoleucine degradation
Folate biosynthesis

4 pathways downregulated by F-ARA2 but not ARA2

leucine and isoleucine biosynthesis
Other glycan degradation
Folate biosynthesis
Ether lipid metabolism

ARA2 and F-ARA 2 also downregulate 13 pathways unaffected by BAP:

Aminoacyl-tRNA biosynthesis
Biosynthesis of amino acids
Lysine biosynthesis
Pyruvate metabolism
Biosynthesis of secondary metabolites
AGE-RAGE signaling pathway in diabetic complications
Biosynthesis of antibiotics
Phosphatidylinositol signaling system
Lysine degradation
RNA transport
Pantothenate and CoA biosynthesis
RNA degradation
Sphingolipid metabolism

10 pathways downregulated by ARA2 but not F-ARA2:

Citrate cycle (TCA cycle)
Glycerophospholipid metabolism
Endocytosis
Oxidative phosphorylation
Glycolysis / Gluconeogenesis
MAPK signaling pathway - yeast
Glycine
serine and threonine metabolism
Butanoate metabolism
Pentose phosphate pathway

Figure S10: Analysis of pathways downregulated in *B. cinerea* following treatment with BAP, ARA2 or F-ARA2.

Analysis was conducted on DEGs identified using the DESeq2 package ($\text{padj} < 0.05$, $\log_2\text{FC} > 1$), using the Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes (KEGG), and the KOBAS 3 Tool. Overlapping pathways are indicated in the Venn diagram, and detailed to the right.

Table S1: Primer pairs used in qRT-PCR

Genes	Locus	Forward	Reverse
<i>CKX2</i> (Cytokinin dehydrogenase 2)	Solyc01g088160	CCCCGAAAATGGTGAAATG	CAAAGTGGCTTGCTTGAACA
<i>CKX5</i> (Cytokinin dehydrogenase 5)	Solyc04g016430	TGTCACTGGTAAAGGAGAGGTG	GAGCAATCCTAGCCCTTGTG
<i>IPT3</i> (Isopentenyl transferase 3)	Solyc01g080150	TTCCATGCTTGATGTGCTTC	GCTTGCTGTCAACGTCAAAA
<i>IPT5</i> (Isopentenyl transferase 5)	Solyc11g066960	CCAGTTGCAGCCAACAGAAT	GACCCCAGTTCTGCCCTCTA
<i>TRRS/6/7</i> (Tomato response regulator 5/6/7)	Solyc03g113720	GGGATTGATGGTTTGAAGGT	ATCTTGCTCAACACCGATGA
<i>TRR8/9b</i> (Tomato response regulator 8/9b)	Solyc02g071220	AGTATGCCGGAAATGACTGG	TGGAACATTTTCCGATGACA
<i>PR1a</i> (Pathogenesis related-1a)	Solyc01g106620	CTGGTGCTGTGAAGATGTGG	TGACCCTAGCACAACCAAGA
<i>LoxD</i> (LipoxygenaseD)	Solyc03g122340	CCATCCTCACCACCCTCATC	TACTCGGGATCGTTCTCGTC
<i>PR1b</i> (Pathogenesis related-1b)	Solyc00g174340	GTGTCCGAGAGGCCAAGCTA	AGGACGTTGTCCGATCCAGTT
<i>Pi1</i> (Pathogen induced 1)	Solyc01g097270	TGCTTAAGGGTGACAAATACACG	ACATTCACATTGTCACCGCA
<i>Pti5</i> (Pto-interacting 5)	Solyc02g077370	GACATGGTGCAGAGATATGG	CTGAAACAGAGGGCGTTCCT
<i>ERF-1</i> (Ethylene-responsive factor 1)	Solyc05g051200	ATTAGGGATTCAACGCGTAA	AGAGACCAAGGACCCCTCAT
<i>PAL</i> (Phenylalanine ammonia lyase)	Solyc09g007900	TCAAGGCAGCTCAGAAGCTC	CTTAGTTGCTGCACGGATGA
<i>CYP</i> (Cyclophilin)	Solyc01g111170	TGAGTGGCTCAACGGAAAGC	CCAACAGCCTCTGCCTTCTTA
<i>RPL8</i> (Ribosomal protein L2)	Solyc10g006580	TGGAGGGCGTACTGAGAAAC	TCATAGCAACACCACGAACC

Table S2: Parameters of DEGs in the transcriptome of CK (BAP) and Arabinoside (ARA2, F-ARA2) treated *B. cinerea*

		BAP ^ ARA2	BAP ^ FARA2	ARA2 ^ FARA2
Upregulated DEGS				
BAP up	910	Set1: 910	Set1: 910	Set1: 1816
ARA2 up	1816	Set2: 1816	Set2: 1898	Set2: 1898
FARA2 up	1898	Overlap: 462	Overlap: 606	Overlap: 928
		Total number of genes: 12195	Total number of genes: 12195	Total number of genes: 12195
BAP ^ ARA2	462	Representation factor: 3.4	Representation factor: 4.3	Representation factor: 3.3
BAP ^ FARA2	606	p < 5.570e-159	p < 1.399e-296	p < 0.000e+00
ARA2 ^ FARA2	928			
Downregulated DEGS				
BAP down	552	Set1: 552	Set1: 552	Set1: 1212
ARA2 down	1212	Set2: 1212	Set2: 1683	Set2: 1683
FARA2 down	1683	Overlap: 252	Overlap: 365	Overlap: 671
		Total number of genes: 12195	Total number of genes: 12195	Total number of genes: 12195
BAP ^ ARA2	252	Representation factor: 4.6	Representation factor: 4.8	Representation factor: 4.0
BAP ^ FARA2	365	p < 9.553e-112	p < 1.904e-188	p < 2.077e-299
ARA2 ^ FARA2	671			

The representation factor is the number of overlapping genes divided by the expected number of overlapping genes drawn from two independent groups. A representation factor > 1 indicates more overlap than expected of two independent groups, a representation factor < 1 indicates less overlap than expected, and a representation factor of 1 indicates that the two groups overlap by the number of genes expected for independent groups of genes.